

Lifestyle Matters is in Mind : Arogyam & Diseases

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Introduction

In Ayurveda, health is defined as not merely an absence of disease. It is a holistic well-being of the individual in physical, mental, social and spiritual level. Amongst these the spiritual and social well-being described as “*Prasannaatmendriya manah*” is most important. The aim of Ayurvedic treatise is bringing normalcy of body tissues (*Dhaatusaamyā*). While defining *Dhaatusaamyā*, *Charaka* has given equal weightage to psychic factors as that of somatic factors. “*Ruchi aahaarakaale, Annaabhilaasha, Vaikaarikaanaam svapnaanaam adarsanam, Sukhena pratibodhanam*” etc. are ample evidences. The disease as well as wellness is related to self. That is why *Charaka* has stated that “*Atmajah cha ayam purushah, Atmajah cha ayam rogah*”.

Need for the Study

This study aims to explore the vital role of mental health within the framework of Ayurveda, emphasizing the interconnections between the mind, spirit, and body. It seeks to examine how lifestyle choices and emotional states not only impact physical health but also contribute to the onset of mental diseases. By elucidating the Ayurvedic perspective on mental disorders, this research advocates for a holistic approach to well-being.

Methods

An analytical review of key Ayurvedic texts, including the *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita* and *Ashtanga Hridaya*, was conducted to extract core concepts related to mental health and its effects on overall wellness. The investigation focuses on the relationship between mental factors (*Sattva, Rajas, Tamas*) and physical constitution (*Vata, Pitta, Kapha*) in the causation and treatment of diseases.

Analysis

- **Mind-Body Link:** Mental health has a significant impact on physical health. Disturbances in the psyche can cause psychosomatic conditions such as stress, hypertension, and digestive issues.
- **Stress and Aama:** Stress leads to the accumulation of *Aama* (toxins), contributing to metabolic syndromes like diabetes, hypertension, and digestive disorders.
- **Psychosomatic Connection:** Ayurveda's understanding of the interplay between mind and body aligns with modern psychosomatic theories.

Special Points

- **Tripod Concept:** Ayurveda views **Mind, Body, and Spirit** as interdependent, much like a tripod. Mental health is essential for sustaining life.
- **Emotions and Physical Health:** Emotions such as fear, anger, and anxiety disturb bodily equilibrium, leading to disease.
- **Psychic Doshas:** Imbalances in *Rajas* and *Tamas* contribute to mental disorders, which can lead to both physical and mental diseases.
- strength determine the strength of the disease.
- Psyche and Soma- the abode of illness.
- **Stress** - An inevitable companion of life.
- **Stress** leads to Emaciation and Immune failure also.
- Pathology of **stress** induced disorders.
- **Stress** leads to metabolic syndrome.
- Effect of **stress** on GI.T system.
- Effect on cardiovascular system.
- Doshic constitution and its management through psychic approach.
- Ayurvedic therapeutic line in psychic disorders.
- Ayurvedic approach of psychosomatic disorders.

Results

- **Psychosomatic Disorders:** Mental disturbances significantly contribute to lifestyle diseases and psychosomatic conditions.
- **Satvabala:** High mental resilience (*Satvabala*) helps individuals better manage both mental and physical illnesses.
- **Holistic Treatment:** Addressing both mental and physical health improves treatment outcomes and overall well-being.
- **Additionally,** stress is identified as a key contributor to lifestyle-related diseases, highlighting the importance of mental well-being in the prevention and management of these conditions.

Discussion

The research indicates that emotional imbalances strongly influence physical disorders. Ancient Ayurvedic principles on mental health align closely with modern understandings of stress and its impact on health. Integrating Ayurvedic principles into modern healthcare can offer more effective treatments for stress-induced diseases.

Conclusion

This study underscores the necessity of integrating *Manasika* health into Ayurvedic practices and public health strategies. By fostering a balanced psyche and addressing emotional *Vikara* (imbalances), individuals can enhance their overall health. The research advocates for a shift toward recognizing the essential link between mental and physical health, which paves the way for more effective holistic interventions. This integrated perspective is crucial for promoting sustainable well-being within the context of modern healthcare frameworks.

References

- *Charaka Samhita* • *Madhav Nidana*
- *Sushruta Samhita* • *Yoga Ratnakar*
- *Ashtanga Sangraha* • *Kashyapa Samhita*
- *Ashtanga Hridaya*
- *Shrimata Bhagavatgeeta*